

DCFO: Density-Based Counterfactuals for Outliers

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Abstract

Outlier detection identifies data points that significantly deviate from the majority of the data distribution. Explaining outliers is crucial for understanding the underlying factors that contribute to their detection, validating their significance, and identifying potential biases or errors. Effective explanations provide actionable insights, facilitating preventive measures to avoid similar outliers in the future. Counterfactual explanations clarify why specific data points are classified as outliers by identifying minimal changes required to alter their prediction. Although valuable, most existing counterfactual explanation methods overlook the unique challenges posed by outlier detection, and fail to target classical, widely adopted outlier detection algorithms. Local Outlier Factor (LOF) is one of the most popular unsupervised outlier detection methods, quantifying outlierness through relative local density. Despite LOF's widespread use across diverse applications, it lacks interpretability. To address this limitation, we introduce *Density-based Counterfactuals for Outliers (DCFO)*, a novel method specifically designed to generate counterfactual explanations for LOF. DCFO partitions the data space into regions where LOF behaves smoothly, enabling efficient gradient-based optimisation. Extensive experimental validation on 50 OpenML datasets demonstrates that DCFO consistently outperforms benchmarked competitors, offering superior proximity and validity of generated counterfactuals.

CCS Concepts

• **Computing methodologies** → **Anomaly detection**; • **Mathematics of computing** → **Computing most probable explanation**.

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Keywords

Counterfactual Explanations; Outlier Explanations; Outlier Detection; Explainable Artificial Intelligence; Interpretable Machine Learning

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1 Introduction

Outliers, or anomalies, are generally defined as a subset of observations that are inconsistent with the rest of the dataset [4, 7, 18, 21, 48, 50, 51]. Detecting these outliers is crucial across numerous applications, including identifying system faults, fraudulent activities, malicious transactions, and sensor malfunctions [21, 35].

Explaining detected anomalies can be a key step in the detection pipeline. The explanation enables stakeholders to understand why the instance was flagged as an outlier, allowing them to take proper action [35]. In an application designed to detect malicious card transactions, a clear explanation can validate the outlier as a genuine attack or identify it as merely an unusual but non-malicious event. Moreover, as in other Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) applications, interpreting the outputs of an outlier detection model builds trust in the model, and understanding the rationale behind its predictions enables actionability when the model does not behave as expected [14]. Despite the importance and impact of outlier detection models, their explanation is often overlooked [50].

Counterfactual (CF) explanations, a popular XAI technique, identify minimal changes required to adjust a model's prediction [39, 46]. In outlier detection contexts, counterfactuals highlight the specific features causing the outlier and suggest actionable modifications to convert anomalous instances into inliers.

For instance, consider an assembly line equipped with numerous temperature and pressure sensors that typically report values

within a consistent range. If one sensor detects a temperature outside this range, a Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [9] model would flag this as anomalous. Stakeholders would then question if this spike indicates a genuine overheating issue or simply a sensor malfunction. A counterfactual explanation would clarify the precise adjustment needed to restore normal readings, guiding practical interventions. A raw LOF score alone would not suffice, as the method provides no attribution of which features are responsible for the outlier and offers no guidance on which changes would be required to bring the measurement back into the normal operating region.

However, standard outlier detection techniques, such as LOF, present significant challenges for traditional counterfactual methods. LOF calculates outlierness based on local density comparisons among neighbouring points. Consequently, small changes in an observation can abruptly change its nearest neighbours, causing discontinuous jumps in outlier scores. Such discontinuities render gradient-based optimisation methods ineffective since they depend on smooth prediction transitions.

Alternative approaches like Bayesian optimisation handle discontinuities by exploring many possibilities without gradients, but their computational cost becomes prohibitive in high-dimensional settings [39]. Counterfactual methods have traditionally targeted classification models. Although outlier detection can be framed this way, it is highly imbalanced, making counterfactual search difficult [50]. Outliers are a small minority, often far from inliers and even from each other [50].

In this work, we propose *Density-based Counterfactuals for Outliers (DCFO)*, a novel counterfactual method designed explicitly for explaining LOF outputs [9]. DCFO exploits the inherent structure of LOF by partitioning the data space into meaningful regions, enabling efficient gradient-based optimisation despite the underlying non-continuous nature of LOF scores. Our method also supports handling non-actionable features, produces diverse counterfactuals, and is able to adjust counterfactuals' plausibility.

Our main contributions include:

- The **first** Local Outlier Factor counterfactual explanation method, DCFO, which partitions the **data space into regions**, and subsequently performs **gradient-based optimisation** to produce counterfactuals.
- DCFO's algorithmic modifications to handle **non-actionable features**, generate multiple **diverse counterfactuals**, and take **plausibility** into account.
- Empirical benchmarks using real-world datasets, showing how DCFO's counterfactuals perform **better** than competitors in terms of **proximity, validity, and diversity**.

We discuss related work in Sect. 2, introduce DCFO in Sect. 3, present experimental results in Sect. 4, and conclude in Sect. 5.

2 Related Work

Unsupervised outlier detection methods identify points which deviate from the norm. Approaches include distance-based methods, which flag points whose distance to their k -nearest neighbours exceeds a predefined threshold, and density-based methods, which consider the sparsity of local neighbourhoods to identify anomalies. A prominent example of the latter is **Local Outlier Factor (LOF)**, which computes an "outlier score", flagging low local density of a

point compared to that of its neighbours [9]. Comparative studies show that LOF is very competitive with popular alternatives like Isolation Forest or deep methods [10, 12, 20].

SLOF [41] replaces reachability distance with inverse k -nearest neighbour distance to reduce time complexity. INFLO [23] incorporates reverse nearest neighbours into the density estimation for more reliable outlier scores in sparse regions. DAO [3] estimates local intrinsic dimensionality and uses a density-estimation adjusted to the estimated local dimensionality. GLOSH [11] uses hierarchical density estimations to detect outliers across multiple density levels.

Other popular outlier detection methods include KNN [37] which assigns an outlier score based on distance to the k -th nearest neighbour, effectively capturing global deviations, and ABOD [27] based on the idea that anomalous points exhibit smaller angle variance to pairs of other points than inliers. Clustering-based methods [47] include k -means++ [13], which integrates clustering and outlier detection by iteratively removing points with the greatest distances from their nearest cluster centroids before updating centroid positions, thereby identifying points far from all clusters as outliers.

Explainable Outlier Detection (XOD) identifies outlying instances and provides explanations for why they are considered outliers. One can consider two categories when considering XOD methods: (i) shallow and symbolic explanations, which explain outliers through features or , and (ii) counterfactual explanations, which reveal how an outlying instance can be modified to become an inlier [30, 35].

Shallow XOD Methods. Early and popular XOD methods focus on describing outliers through feature attributions, summaries and logical rules. One of the earliest works is from Knorr et al. with their notion of intensional knowledge [25]. Rather than simply finding an outlier, their method identifies a minimal set of attribute constraints isolating the instance from its nearest neighbours. For example, an outlying and potentially fraudulent credit card transaction may be explained by $\{\text{Amount} > 1,000, \text{HourOfDay} < 6\}$, where the two conditions separate the transaction from its nearest non-fraud examples in the feature space.

Anguilli et al. [5] define outlying properties by quantifying how extreme each attribute and outlier values are relative to the overall distribution. Müller et al. [33] extend this notion to OutRules, generating logical rules across multiple contexts; characterising outlying behaviour within each context. While these methods provide symbolic explanations, they provide only static descriptions of "why" an outlier is an outlier, but do not include actionable changes, i.e., "how" to fix the outliers.

Counterfactual Explanations. A counterfactual explanation for an outlier would answer "How could this outlier be modified to appear normal?". Answering the important "how" question is crucial for outlier detection as it provides insight into why an instance is an outlier and how it can be "fixed".

Some methods use counterfactuals for anomaly detection [17, 31], e.g., generating healthy brains as counterfactuals to detect anomalies in brain images [17], while most focus on explaining identified outliers. Several methods for explaining outliers focus on data types like time series or categorical data. Counterfactual ensemble explanations [42] explain time series identified as anomalous by a detection method. The approach is limited to differentiable anomaly detection methods. Trifunov et al. [43] propose an attribution

scheme based on the Maximally Divergent Interval algorithm. The idea consists in changing a subset of features to align with the respective feature distribution of the time series and recalculate how the anomaly changed. Context preserving Algorithmic Recourse for Anomalies in Tabular data (CARAT) [15] is a transformer-based encoder-decoder model, solely for categorical data.

More recently, methods solving counterfactual generation as an optimisation problem based on newly defined loss functions have been proposed. Explain Anomaly via Counterfactual Explanations (EACE) [50] is an approach based on optimising a loss function which includes a classification change term, a density term, and a boundary loss component. The density is estimated through LOF. To solve the optimisation problem, they propose a genetic algorithm and thus, EACE can work also with non differentiable models like LOF. The proposed genetic algorithm performs suboptimally in datasets where outlying instances are not extremely distant from other points [50]. Angiulli et al. [4] propose Masking Models for Outlier Explanation (M^2OE): a deep-neural network guided by an ad-hoc loss function. The generated explanations consist of a set of features and a respective set of changes. The loss function incorporates the isolation of the input outlier before and after applying the generated mask within the subspace defined by the features choice.

DiCE [32] and FACE [36] are two popular counterfactual methods focusing on providing diverse and feasible proposals respectively. DiCE’s gradient-based optimisation makes it unfeasible for LOF. FACE instead requires a density connected path between between the instance to explain and the counterfactual, making it thus unfeasible for isolated outliers.

Another approach to counterfactual explanations is solving a feasible path finding problem, i.e., constructing a path from the data point to be explained towards the counterfactual. Two methods employ LOF to solve this problem. Yamao et al. [49] sequentially change the input feature vector until it obtains the desired classification result, employing a cost function based on LOF to assess feasibility and actionability of the path. Their proposal struggles with validity and does not account for non-actionable features.

DACE [24] follows a similar approach: to obtain a feasible perturbed vector, they introduce a cost function considering feature correlation and data distribution solved with mixed-integer linear optimization. To account for the data distribution they employ LOF. DACE focuses on additive classifiers only.

Baycon [39] is a counterfactual method that uses probabilistic feature sampling and Bayesian optimisation. Its objective balances similarity in feature and output space while minimising the number of modified features. While not designed specifically for outliers, Baycon is widely used in our benchmarks, and its Bayesian formulation makes it well-suited for non-differential models like LOF.

Closely related to counterfactuals is the idea of outlier correction, i.e., transforming outliers into inliers. Ji et al. [22] use generative models to achieve this by producing diffusion-based counterfactuals, with a primary focus on diffusion techniques.

3 Methods

The goal of DCFO is to generate counterfactual explanations for outliers identified by Local Outlier Factor (LOF). In this section, we first introduce LOF. Next, we present our proposed DCFO method

and outline the steps for generating multiple diverse counterfactuals. Finally, we demonstrate how DCFO addresses non-actionable features and the plausibility of the proposed counterfactuals.

3.1 Local Outlier Factor

Local Outlier Factor [9] scores the outlierness of points based on their relative density, i.e., comparing their density with that of their neighbours. A point, whose density is comparable with that of its neighbours, has an LOF score of approximately 1. The lower the density of the point compared to its neighbours, the higher the outlierness. The original paper suggests a threshold of 1.5 as good practice for separating inliers and outliers, i.e., a point is identified as an outlier if the average density of its neighbours is one and a half times higher than the density of the point itself. Another common practice for setting the threshold is to take a small quantile of the LOF scores distribution, e.g., 0.1, or to transform the scores into probabilities, improving their interpretability [38].

We assume \mathcal{D} to be a dataset comprising n data points $\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_n$. The notation \mathbf{x} represents a location (or point) in the feature space \mathcal{X} . The function d denotes the distance measure used to compute how far apart two points are in the feature space.

To evaluate the LOF score of a point \mathbf{p} , we need to first compute its k -distance, i.e., the distance of its k -th nearest neighbour. k is the singular parameter required by LOF, and defines the notion of density by defining the neighbourhood of a point. We denote the set of k nearest neighbours of a point \mathbf{p}_i as $knn(\mathbf{p}_i)$.

To reduce statistical fluctuations among nearby points, the LOF algorithm employs the reachability distance which is designed to stabilise density estimates. The reachability distance $rd_k(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j)$ between points \mathbf{p}_i and \mathbf{p}_j is defined as:

$$rd_k(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j) = \max \{k\text{-distance}(\mathbf{p}_j), d(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j)\}. \quad (1)$$

Specifically, when a point \mathbf{p}_j lies closer than the k -distance of \mathbf{p}_j from \mathbf{p}_i , the reachability distance $rd_k(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j)$ is set to k -distance(\mathbf{p}_j). This adjustment mitigates noise from very close points and yields more robust outlier scores [9].

LOF’s notion of local density is represented by the local reachability density (lrd_k) of a point \mathbf{p}_i :

$$lrd_k(\mathbf{p}_i) = \frac{k}{\sum_{\mathbf{p}_j \in knn(\mathbf{p}_i)} rd_k(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_j)}, \quad (2)$$

which is the inverse of the average reachability distance from \mathbf{p}_i to its neighbours. The LOF score of \mathbf{p}_i is defined as:

$$\text{LOF}(\mathbf{p}_i) = \frac{1}{k \cdot lrd_k(\mathbf{p}_i)} \cdot \sum_{\mathbf{p}_j \in knn(\mathbf{p}_i)} lrd_k(\mathbf{p}_j). \quad (3)$$

Hence, in Eq. 3, LOF compares the local density of a point \mathbf{p}_i , captured by its local reachability density (lrd), with the average lrd of its k nearest neighbours. Formally, any \mathbf{p}_i with $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{p}_i) > t$ is labelled as an outlier.

3.2 Density-based Counterfactuals for Outliers

Density-based Counterfactuals for Outliers (DCFO) generates counterfactual proposals for data points flagged as outliers by LOF. Given an outlier point \mathbf{p}_i , our goal is to find a nearby point \mathbf{x} in the feature space such that, if \mathbf{p}_i were hypothetically moved to \mathbf{x} , its LOF score

would fall below the outlier threshold t . Thus, in the following, $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{x})$ refers to the LOF score that would be assigned to \mathbf{p}_i if it were hypothetically located at position \mathbf{x} .

To evaluate $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{x})$ in this context, we compute the score at location \mathbf{x} , treating \mathbf{x} as a new data point and excluding the original \mathbf{p}_i from all k -NN computations. This ensures that \mathbf{x} is judged solely based on its local environment in feature space.

Formally, denoting the resulting counterfactual as $cf(\mathbf{p}_i)$, we solve the following constrained optimisation problem:

$$cf(\mathbf{p}_i) = \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}} d(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{p}_i) \quad | \quad \text{LOF}(\mathbf{x}) \leq t \quad (4)$$

In Eq. 4, the optimisation problem seeks the smallest possible change, measured with distance d , that transforms an outlier into an inlier under the LOF model. As distance metric, we use Euclidean, as it is widely used and the default in LOF. However, a key challenge is that the constraint ($\text{LOF}(\mathbf{x}) \leq t$) is not differentiable, preventing the use of standard gradient-based optimisers.

To address this, we partition the data space into regions where the LOF score behaves continuously and is differentiable. Within each region, we can apply gradient-based optimisation techniques to search for valid counterfactuals efficiently.

To compute the LOF score of a candidate point \mathbf{x} , we need more than just the location of \mathbf{x} itself. According to Eq. 2 and Eq. 3, the LOF score depends on the local reachability densities of \mathbf{x} and of its k nearest neighbours. In turn, these densities require access to each neighbour's neighbourhood. Therefore, to evaluate $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{x})$, we must identify (i) the k nearest neighbours of \mathbf{x} , denoted as $knn(\mathbf{x})$, and (ii) for each neighbour $\mathbf{p}_j \in knn(\mathbf{x})$, their respective k nearest neighbours $knn(\mathbf{p}_j)$.

This neighbourhood structure defines a unique *key* that characterises a region of the space. Given point \mathbf{x} , its key is: $\mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}) \equiv (knn(\mathbf{x}), knn(\mathbf{p}_j) \forall \mathbf{p}_j \in knn(\mathbf{x}))$. This key encodes all data points whose positions influence the LOF score of \mathbf{x} . We then define a region R_K as the set of all points sharing the same key K :

$$R_K \equiv \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X} \mid \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}) = K\}. \quad (5)$$

These regions R_K form a partition of the input space, such that within each region, the set of points relevant to LOF computations remains fixed. This property ensures, as will be proved in the following, that the LOF score varies smoothly within a region, making it suitable for gradient-based optimisation. As stated above, $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{x})$, and the space partition, depends on the point \mathbf{p}_i being moved.

Note that the symbol K used to denote a region's key is unrelated to the lowercase k used in LOF to indicate the number of neighbours. Also, if the key were defined using only $knn(\mathbf{x})$ (and not the neighbours-of-neighbours), the resulting partition would correspond to a k -th order Voronoi diagram, i.e., a decomposition of the space based on each point's k nearest neighbours in the dataset.

DCFO does not require computing the whole partition of the feature space in advance. Instead, it only estimates the key $\mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x})$ for selected points encountered during optimisation. This design choice is crucial for scalability as computing the complete k -th order Voronoi diagram is known to be computationally expensive, especially in high dimensions [6]. The regions defined by Eq. 5 are more complex than standard Voronoi cells, since they depend not

Figure 1: DCFO region-based space partitioning for synthetic 2d data (black: data points, red: \mathbf{p}_i outlier to be explained, threshold = 1.10). Dashed circles denote k -distance neighbourhoods ($k = 2$). Background colours uniquely indicate LOF regions. The blue point is the result of the first constrained optimisation, lying outside the initial region and still above the threshold ($\text{LOF} = 1.11$). A second optimisation starting from that point produces the green counterfactual, which remains within a single region and satisfies the threshold ($\text{LOF} = 1.10$). Arrows indicate the optimisation path.

only on $knn(\mathbf{x})$ but also on the neighbours of each neighbour. Constructing the entire space partition would, therefore, be inefficient and unnecessary.

Figure 1 illustrates the partitioning induced by keys $\mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x})$ on a 2D synthetic dataset. The dataset \mathcal{D} is sampled from a standard bivariate normal distribution. The red point \mathbf{p}_i denotes the outlier for which a counterfactual is to be computed, while the black points represent other points in the dataset. The neighbourhood size is set to $k = 2$. The dashed circles illustrate the k -distance neighbourhood of each point $\mathbf{p}_j \in \mathcal{D}$. Each coloured region corresponds to a unique key K , i.e., all points in a region share the same nearest neighbours and second-order neighbours.

Critically, within each region R_K , assuming a well-behaved distance function such as the Euclidean distance used in LOF, the LOF score is a differentiable function of \mathbf{x} . More precisely, we denote $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x})$ as the LOF score computed using the fixed neighbourhood structure encoded by key K . This function is differentiable almost

everywhere in \mathcal{X} , which allows us to perform efficient gradient-based optimisation:

PROPOSITION 3.1. *Let d be a well-behaved distance function. Then, $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x})$ is continuous and differentiable almost everywhere. Specifically, if d is twice continuously differentiable, then $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x})$ is twice continuously differentiable almost everywhere.*

The intuition behind Proposition 3.1 is that in a region R_K , all neighbour sets used by LOF remain fixed. Consequently, every term that contributes to $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x})$, i.e., the distances $d(\mathbf{x}, y_i)$, the reachability distances $rd_k(\mathbf{x}, y_i)$, and the local reachability density $lrd_k(\mathbf{x})$ changes smoothly as \mathbf{x} moves. In the reachability distance definition, $\max\{k\text{-distance}(y_i), d(\mathbf{x}, y_i)\}$ implies that when the two terms are equal, the studied function is continuous but not differentiable. This only happens for a set of points having measure 0, making the function differentiable almost everywhere.

PROOF. Marking with knn_K the set of neighbours of \mathbf{x} , which are contained in key K , we need to prove that

$$\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{k \cdot lrd_k(\mathbf{x})} \cdot \sum_{y_i \in knn_K} lrd_k(y_i) \quad ,$$

is twice continuously differentiable in the variable \mathbf{x} . Exploiting the property that the sum of differentiable functions is still differentiable, and leaving out the constant from the differentiation process, we are left to prove that

$$\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{lrd_k(y_1)}{lrd_k(\mathbf{x})}$$

is differentiable. Without loss of generality, we consider a specific element of knn_K , i.e., y_1 . Note that in general $lrd_k(y_1)$ does depend on \mathbf{x} , as \mathbf{x} could be one of the neighbours of y_1 . If \mathbf{x} is not one of the neighbours of y_1 , then $lrd_k(y_1)$ is just a constant and proving that $lrd_k(\mathbf{x})$ is twice continuously differentiable will suffice. We start by treating the denominator, i.e., $lrd_k(\mathbf{x})$:

$$lrd_k(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{k}{\sum_{y_i \in knn_K} rd_k(\mathbf{x}, y_i)}$$

Exploiting again the properties of differentiable functions and choosing again, without loss of generality, $y_i = y_1$, we are left to look at $rd_k(\mathbf{x}, y_1) = \max\{k\text{-distance}(y_1), d(\mathbf{x}, y_1)\}$.

Given the assumptions on the distance function d , both terms in $k\text{-distance}(y_1)$ and $d(\mathbf{x}, y_1)$ are twice continuously differentiable. In all the points \mathbf{z}_i such that $k\text{-distance}(y_1) = d(\mathbf{x}, y_1)$, $rd_k(\mathbf{x}, y_1)$ is continuous, as both $k\text{-distance}(y_1)$ and $d(\mathbf{x}, y_1)$ have the same value in \mathbf{z}_i . $rd_k(\mathbf{x}, y_1)$ though, is in general non-differentiable in \mathbf{z}_i , as the limit toward \mathbf{z}_i of the derivative of $rd_k(\mathbf{x}, y_1)$ might differ depending on from where \mathbf{z}_i is approached. Critically, the set of points \mathbf{z}_i , has measure 0. Indeed, it is generated from the equality constraint $k\text{-distance}(y_1) - d(\mathbf{x}, y_1) = 0$. If our dataset \mathcal{D} lies in \mathcal{R}^m , the subset of points \mathbf{z}_i will thus lie in a lower dimensional space \mathcal{R}^{m-1} . Thus, $rd_k(\mathbf{x}, y_1)$ and consequently $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x})$, will be twice continuously differentiable except for a set of points with measure 0, i.e., almost everywhere. A similar reasoning applies to $lrd_k(y_1)$ which has at most one reachability distance \mathbf{x} -dependent term at the denominator which is differentiable almost everywhere. \square

The algorithmic definition of DCFO is thus as follows. The method takes as inputs: **(i)** the outlier \mathbf{p}_i (i.e., a point in \mathcal{D} with $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{p}_i) > t$), **(ii)** the LOF parameter k , **(iii)** the threshold t used to classify outliers, and **(iv)** the distance function d .

The first step of the algorithm is to compute the key $K = \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{p}_i)$, which defines the region R_K . We then solve the constrained optimisation problem in Eq. 4, replacing the original constraint $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{x}) \leq t$ with the relaxed, region-specific constraint $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x}) \leq t$.

Because $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x})$ is differentiable almost everywhere (Proposition 3.1), we apply a gradient-based optimisation method. We use Sequential Least Squares Programming (SLSQP) [26, 34], an efficient constrained optimiser that handles inequality constraints.

During the optimisation, if SLSQP explores a point \mathbf{x} that lies outside the original region, we store it in a First-In-First-Out (FIFO) exploration queue for later evaluation. Once SLSQP converges to a solution \mathbf{x}_f , we check whether the final point remains within the original region. We compute the key $K' = \mathcal{K}(\mathbf{x}_f)$ and distinguish two cases. *Case one:* If $K' = K$, then $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x}_f) = \text{LOF}(\mathbf{x}_f)$, so the constraint is valid, and we return \mathbf{x}_f as the counterfactual $cf(\mathbf{p}_i)$. *Case two:* If $K' \neq K$, the constraint $\text{LOF}_K(\mathbf{x}_f) \leq t$ no longer guarantees that $\text{LOF}(\mathbf{x}_f) \leq t$, as the neighbourhood has changed. In this case, we recursively restart the algorithm using \mathbf{x}_f as the new starting point, now operating in region $R_{K'}$.

To avoid redundant computation, if K' has already been the start of an optimisation, we dequeue the next unexplored point and attempt optimisation from there. The recursion terminates in two scenarios, **(i)** the optimiser finds a valid counterfactual in the current region, **(ii)** all candidates in the exploration queue have been exhausted without success. The step by step algorithm is outlined in Algorithm 1.

Thus, DCFO exploits the structure of the LOF function to generate high-quality counterfactuals using efficient, gradient-based optimisation. Algorithm 1 outlines how to find the counterfactual closest to the original outlier in terms of distance. A modified version of this algorithm, capable of producing multiple diverse counterfactuals, is described in Section 3.3.

An illustrative example of DCFO's optimisation process is shown in Figure 1. The threshold for outlieriness is set to $t = 1.10$, and the red point represents the outlier \mathbf{p}_i with an initial LOF score of 1.89.

The purple arrows show the optimisation steps of DCFO. The first solution (blue point) lies in a different region than the starting one, seen by the different background colours, but still violates the threshold ($\text{LOF} = 1.11$). A second optimisation run (starting from that point) produces the final counterfactual (green point), which lies within the same region, and now satisfies the constraint ($\text{LOF} = 1.10 = t$). This example demonstrates that DCFO does not require computing the full space partition in advance; instead, it only evaluates a small number of points.

3.3 Proposing Multiple Counterfactuals

The procedure described in Algorithm 1 returns a single counterfactual. However, in many decision-making contexts, stakeholders may wish to consider multiple alternatives. Since actionability depends on constraints or preferences varying across users, offering a diverse set of counterfactuals improves the likelihood of identifying a feasible and meaningful proposal.

Algorithm 1: DCFO($p_i, d, k, \mathcal{D}, t$)

Input : Outlier p_i , distance function d , LOF parameter k , dataset \mathcal{D} , threshold t .
Output: Counterfactual, $cf(p_i)$
 Initialise empty starting regions' queue, StartList $\leftarrow []$;
 Initialise empty exploration queue, ExpList \leftarrow FIFO $[]$;
 Compute key $K = \mathcal{K}(p_i)$;
 StartList.append(K) ;
 Find x_f solving $\min_{x \in \mathcal{X}} d(x, p_i) \mid \text{LOF}_K(x) \leq t$, using SLSQP;
 Compute key $K' = \mathcal{K}(x_f)$;
if $K' = K$ **then**
 | **return** x_f ;
end
else if $K' \neq K$ **then**
 | **if** $K' \notin \text{StartList}$ **then**
 | | StartList.append(K') ;
 | | **return** DCFO(x_f) ;
 | **end**
 | **else if** $K' \in \text{StartList}$ **then**
 | | $x_i \leftarrow \text{ExpList}.\text{pop}()$;
 | | **return** DCFO(x_i) ;
 | **end**
end

Moreover, simply generating many counterfactuals close to one another does not provide additional explanatory value. If counterfactuals are only infinitesimally different from one another, they are effectively indistinguishable in practice [29]. Prior work in explainability similarly emphasises the importance of diversity [32, 40].

To generate multiple, diverse, and still proximal counterfactuals, we make use of the region-based partition of the input space. After identifying the optimal counterfactual using Algorithm 1, we revisit the regions explored during the optimisation process. For each region not yet associated with an accepted counterfactual, we initiate a new constrained optimisation. Each new counterfactual is accepted if it belongs to a region that has not yet proposed any counterfactual, ensuring diversity by construction.

The final result is a set of counterfactuals that are *diverse*, since each counterfactual is based on a distinct key $\mathcal{K}(x)$, and *proximal*, since each counterfactual is the result of a distance optimisation.

If a user requests a fixed number c of counterfactuals, the process stops once c valid counterfactuals are found or the region queue is exhausted. As new regions are encountered during these secondary optimisations, they are added to the exploration list and considered if further counterfactuals are requested. The complete procedure is shown in the Appendix A, Algorithm 2.

3.4 Non-Actionable Features

In many real-world datasets, certain features are immutable or extremely difficult to change, such as age. These are referred to as *non-actionable features* [8, 19, 45]. If a counterfactual proposes changes to such features, it becomes infeasible for users to act upon, thereby invalidating its purpose. For instance, an outlier cannot be

corrected if the suggested fix involves changing attributes that the user cannot modify.

To address this, DCFO allows users to specify which features are actionable and which are not. The algorithm is modified accordingly: while distances and neighbourhoods are still computed in the whole feature space, the SLSQP optimiser is restricted to adjust only the actionable variables. The restriction ensures that non-actionable features remain fixed at their original values, and the counterfactual modifies only the permitted subset to maximise proximity.

3.5 Plausibility

Plausibility is a critical quality for counterfactuals, as proposed instances should be realistic and attainable. A common criticism of many counterfactual methods is that they produce solutions outside the empirical data distribution [24, 46, 50], making them likely infeasible or non-actionable. Specifically, if the counterfactual lies in a region of the feature space where no other instances are, it might imply that the region is challenging to reach, and the counterfactual may not be feasible.

Fortunately, plausibility integrates naturally into DCFO, particularly because it operates on top of LOF. A widely accepted proxy for plausibility is data density: points that lie in high-density regions are more likely to be realistic and interpretable [24]. Since LOF scores are inversely related to relative local density, high LOF values indicate low-density (isolated) regions, while low LOF values indicate high-density (typical) areas. Targeting a lower LOF score during optimisation naturally encourages plausibility. In other words, a point with a low LOF score lies in a region of the space with many similar instances. These regions are more likely to reflect realistic and feasible scenarios, as they represent common structures in the data. Therefore, by setting a stricter constraint on the LOF score (e.g., requiring $\text{LOF}(x) \leq 1.25$ when the threshold is $t = 1.5$), DCFO can be steered toward generating counterfactuals that lie in denser, and hence more plausible areas of the feature space. In this way, DCFO not only provides proximity and diversity, but also generates counterfactuals that are grounded in realistic, high-density regions.

4 Experiments

In this section, we empirically evaluate the quality of DCFO's counterfactual explanations using metrics from the counterfactual explanation literature [19]: *proximity* (closeness between point and explanation), *validity* (the proportion of valid counterfactuals), and *diversity* (how different the proposed counterfactuals are). In addition, we assess the *robustness* of DCFO when handling non-actionable features. Throughout all experiments, distances are computed using Euclidean distance, consistent with LOF's default implementation. Appendix C details a full time complexity analysis.

The experiments compare DCFO with three state-of-the-art methods. **(i)** Baycon, a model-agnostic counterfactual method that leverages Bayesian optimisation, handling non-differentiable models [39]; **(ii)** EACE, a model-agnostic method explicitly designed for explaining outliers by generating counterfactuals close to the boundary separating outliers from inliers [50]; **(iii)** Baseline, a naïve approach that moves an outlier directly to the position of the nearest inlier. We considered other model-agnostic methods such as DiCE [32] and FACE [36], but these approaches are not applicable

Table 1: Validity across all outliers for 10 representative datasets. The full table with 50 datasets is available in extended material [2]. A score of 1 indicates a valid counterfactual was found for every outlier.

	k	DCFO	Baycon	EACE	Baseline
sonar (S)	10	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
liver-disorders (L)	10	1.00	1.00	0.56	1.00
diabetes (D)	10	1.00	1.00	0.33	1.00
triazines (T)	15	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.90
basketball (B)	15	1.00	1.00	0.00	1.00
glass (G)	15	1.00	0.56	0.39	0.75
ar3 (A)	15	1.00	0.73	0.09	1.00
disclosure x noise (DN)	15	1.00	1.00	0.50	1.00
ionosphere (I)	10	1.00	0.15	0.13	0.41
chscase census2 (C)	10	1.00	1.00	0.50	1.00

to LOF-based outlier detection and therefore are not included in our comparison.

Experiments are conducted using 50 diverse datasets from the OpenML repository [44]. Chosen datasets cover different domains, number of instances in the range 16 : 53940, and dataset dimensionality in the range 2 : 124. Reproducible code is available at: <https://github.com/tommasoamico/DCFO>. Tables in the following present results for 10 representative datasets, full details for all 50 datasets are available in the extended material [2]. Critical Difference (CD) diagrams are computed using results for all 50 datasets.

4.1 Quality of DCFO’s Counterfactuals

We measure counterfactual quality in terms of proximity and validity. LOF is computed using Euclidean distance, and we randomly select the neighbourhood parameter (k) from the set: {10, 15, 20}, to demonstrate DCFO’s robustness to LOF’s parameter choice.

The LOF threshold, which separates inliers from outliers, is initially set to 1.5, following standard practice [9]. If no points exceed this threshold, we set the threshold at the 95th percentile of LOF scores, ensuring about 5% of points are classified as outliers.

For each identified outlier, we run DCFO, Baycon, EACE and the Baseline method. LOF acts as a binary classifier, labelling points as outliers if their LOF scores exceed the threshold. DCFO generates valid counterfactuals by ensuring the new LOF score is below this threshold. Baycon by default generates multiple CF candidates.

Validity. Counterfactuals are valid if the generated points are not identified as outliers. We report the proportion of outliers for which a counterfactual is identified for each dataset. A validity of 1 means that the method can find a counterfactual for every outlier, while a validity of 0 indicates that the method did not find counterfactuals.

Table 1 reports results for 10 representative datasets; the full collection of 50 datasets is available in extended material [2] and discussed in Appendix B. Overall average validities are 1.00 for DCFO, 0.84 for Baycon, 0.38 for EACE, and 0.88 for the Baseline.

The average validity shows that DCFO provides counterfactual explanations for every outlier detected, achieving validity 1. In contrast, the other methods fall short, with EACE performing the

Figure 2: 2d data drawn from standard normal distribution with LOF scores for $k = 2$. Left: Original: outlier (red) has higher LOF score than its closest inlier (green), despite being closer to most data. Right: After Baseline counterfactual move: outlier superimposed on closest inlier (red with shared increased LOF score above threshold).

weakest. This difference stems from how DCFO exploits the internal structure of LOF, by aligning the counterfactual search with LOF’s density-ratio formulation, DCFO is able to construct a valid counterfactual for every outlier across all 50 datasets. The competing methods lack such alignment and, due to the non-continuous and relative-density nature of LOF, they frequently fail to produce counterfactuals that cross the anomaly threshold.

Moreover, note how our proposed baseline, despite its intuitive appeal, is not always guaranteed to provide a valid counterfactual. Because of LOF’s use of relative densities and reachability distances, the resulting score can remain above the anomaly threshold even after moving the outlier to the closest inlier. To clarify why the Baseline heuristic can yield invalid counterfactuals, we provide an illustrative example.

A toy dataset of 10 instances is drawn from a two dimensional standard normal distribution. Then, LOF is fitted with $k = 2$. The dataset along with the LOF scores are displayed on Figure 2. The dotted lines represent the neighbourhood of a point, i.e., the circle having the point as the centre, and the point’s k -distance as the radius. The outlier to analyse is marked in red (threshold = 1.5), while the closest inlier is drawn in green.

It might seem unintuitive that the red point in Figure 2 has a higher LOF score than the green point. This happens because the red point’s second neighbour is in a very high density region, having a low LOF value of 0.86. This makes the red point’s relative density lower than the green point’s relative density.

We generate a counterfactual using the introduced Baseline method. The outlier is thus moved to the closest inlier, with the two points that will have a new common LOF score. Figure 2 right view, shows the new setting, with the two superimposed points marked in red, having an LOF score of 1.56, higher than the inlier’s previous LOF score and above the set threshold.

The reason for the new LOF score being higher than that of the inlier can be mainly be attributed to the higher density (more precisely of the local reachability density) of the original inlier point in the new setting. Specifically, as written in Equation 2, the

Table 2: Proximity. μ : mean Euclidean distance of outlier to closest valid counterfactual (*NA*: none valid), $\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$: standard error of the mean across each outlier for every dataset (*NA*: one valid counterfactual only). Lower is better. k : neighbourhood size in LOF. 10 representative datasets out of 50 total, the full table is available in the extended material [2].

	k	DCFO	Baycon	EACE	Baseline
		$\mu \pm \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$	$\mu \pm \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$	$\mu \pm \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$	$\mu \pm \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$
S	10	0.62 \pm NA	1.59 \pm NA	20.02 \pm NA	9.14 \pm NA
L	10	0.15 \pm 0.04	0.22 \pm 0.05	1.3 \pm 0.2	1.06 \pm 0.07
D	10	0.29 \pm 0.05	0.47 \pm 0.07	1.7 \pm 0.2	2.2 \pm 0.1
T	15	4.2 \pm 0.6	7.9 \pm 0.7	NA	10.7 \pm 0.7
B	15	1.16 \pm NA	2.29 \pm NA	NA	1.76 \pm NA
G	15	0.4 \pm 0.2	0.7 \pm 0.4	2.5 \pm 0.5	1.4 \pm 0.4
A	15	0.62 \pm NA	0.74 \pm NA	3.42 \pm NA	2.33 \pm NA
DN	15	0.07 \pm 0.02	0.15 \pm 0.03	0.8 \pm 0.1	0.81 \pm 0.05
I	10	0.2 \pm 0.1	0.4 \pm 0.1	6 \pm 1	2.5 \pm 0.2
C	10	0.30 \pm 0.05	0.59 \pm 0.09	1.9 \pm 0.2	2.27 \pm 0.09

lrd is the inverse of the average reachability distance of a point to its neighbours. In the case of the inlier, its two neighbours are the original outlier, which is now superimposed with the original inlier, and the point having an LOF score of 0.96.

Despite the outlier coming closer to the inlier, the reachability distance from the original inlier to the original outlier increases. This is because the outlier’s k -distance increases, evident from the radius of the dotted circles, and it is higher than the Euclidean distance between the two points, which is 0. The reachability distance to the second neighbour stays instead the same, as the two points do not move and their Euclidean distance is higher than the second neighbour’s k -distance. Thus, the *lrd* of the inlier decreases due to its k -distance to the closest neighbour (original outlier) increasing, causing the LOF to increase above the threshold.

Proximity. Proximity denotes how similar the counterfactual is to the original data point, this is measured as the Euclidean distance between them. Thus, we select the closest valid counterfactual, i.e., a point with an LOF score below the threshold; if none are valid, Baycon’s proposal is marked as invalid. Equivalently, if EACE does not provide any valid candidate, the validity for EACE is zero. The baseline directly moves the outlier to the nearest inlier, but does not guarantee validity due to LOF’s relative density calculations as shown in Figure 2.

Table 2 reports proximity results for 10 datasets. The average distance of the counterfactual with the lowest proximity for each outlier is highlighted in bold. If a method does not find any valid counterfactual for a given dataset, it’s marked with Not Available (NA). Moreover, for each dataset we display LOF’s k parameter. The table containing all 50 datasets can be found in in extended material [2], as discussed in Appendix B.

As a result, we see in Table 2 that DCFO consistently achieves superior proximity scores compared to other methods, demonstrating enhanced actionability and feasibility.

Figure 3: Proximity CD diagram across methods. DCFO ranks first with statistically significant results (Nemenyi’s test). Baycon is second, trailed by Baseline and EACE whose differences are not significant.

To facilitate comparison across datasets with varying dimensionalities, we utilise a CD diagram [16], seen in Fig. 3. The CD diagram uses a Nemenyi post-hoc test to determine if observed differences in average ranks are statistically significant.

In our evaluation across all 50 datasets, the methods are ranked according to their proximity performance, with rank 1 assigned to the method that, on average, proposes the closest valid counterfactual for a given dataset, and rank 4 to the one with the furthest.

In Figure 3 the horizontal bar in the diagram denotes the minimum difference required for significance at $p < 0.05$. Methods whose average ranks are not significantly different are connected by a thick horizontal line. DCFO achieves the best average rank and, according to Nemenyi’s test, the difference to the second-best method, Baycon, is statistically significant. Baycon ranks second, followed by the proposed Baseline and EACE. The difference between the Baseline and EACE is not statistically significant.

4.2 Diversity of Counterfactuals

In practical scenarios, providing multiple actionable alternatives is often desirable. To evaluate DCFO’s capability to generate multiple diverse counterfactuals, we use the diversity metric from Mothilal et al. [32]. Specifically, we compute a kernel matrix $K_{ij} = 1/(1 + d(cf_i, cf_j))$ and use its determinant as a measure of diversity: higher determinant values indicate greater diversity among proposed counterfactuals. For consistency, 10 counterfactuals per instance are taken for each method, following their respective generative mechanisms.

We benchmark DCFO against Baycon and EACE, selecting for EACE the first 10 valid counterfactuals it provides. Baycon, lacking direct control over the number of counterfactuals proposed, is assessed in two ways: using the 10 closest counterfactuals and a random selection of 10 counterfactuals from its proposals. DCFO inherently prioritises proximity in its diversity generation, maintaining actionable solutions close to the original instance.

To provide an interpretable assessment of diversity, we rank methods based on their determinant scores and visualise using the CD diagram (Figure 4). A score of zero denotes when a method fails to produce multiple counterfactuals, thus, ranking last. In Figure 4, we clearly see DCFO’s statistically significant advantage in diversity compared to the other methods. Randomly selected counterfactuals from Baycon and EACE exhibit similar diversity, while Baycon’s 10 closest solutions offer the least diversity.

Figure 4: CD diagram comparing diversity among counterfactual generation methods. DCFO ranks highest with statistically significant differences.

4.3 Impact of Non-Actionable Features on Counterfactual Generation

Real-world applications often limit the actionability of certain features. We evaluate DCFO’s effectiveness when subsets of features are deemed non-actionable, measuring both proximity and validity across the selected datasets. Specifically, we randomly define a subset of non-actionable features for all 50 datasets, ensuring they never exceed half the total features.

Then, a further random process chooses which features cannot be altered. Once the set of non-actionable features is chosen, for each outlier, a counterfactual is proposed with both DCFO and Baycon: the two methods that can account for non-actionable features. Quality is assessed through closeness to the original instance (proximity) and proportion of valid counterfactuals (validity).

Results for 10 randomly chosen datasets are provided in Tables 3 and 4, the column %NAF reports the percentage of non-actionable features for the given dataset. For validity, we also report the average across all datasets which is 0.87 for DCFO and 0.73 for Baycon.

The tables demonstrate DCFO’s robustness, consistently outperforming Baycon in terms of proximity and validity; although some cases present increased complexity that reduces validity. This reduction highlights the challenge posed by feature constraints, underlining DCFO’s superior capability in handling non-actionable feature scenarios compared to existing methods. As discussed for all 50 datasets in Appendix B, DCFO outperforms Baycon in terms of proximity in all but two datasets. The full proximity and validity tables are provided in extended material [2].

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Outlier detection is vital in many domains, yet explanations for why instances are flagged as outliers are often overlooked. Such explanations are essential to validate model outputs, understand their reasoning, and guide appropriate action.

We introduced DCFO, a counterfactual method designed to explain predictions made by LOF, a widely used density-based outlier detector. By leveraging LOF’s internal structure, DCFO generates high-quality counterfactuals that correct outliers, account for non-actionable features, ensure plausibility, and offer multiple proposals. It does so by partitioning the input space into regions where LOF behaves more smoothly.

Through extensive experiments, we benchmarked DCFO on real-world datasets against competing methods. We evaluated counterfactual quality using proximity (closeness to the original point),

Table 3: Proximity for limited actionable features. %NAF: percentage of non-actionable features; μ : mean Euclidean distance of outlier to closest valid counterfactual (NA: none valid), $\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$: standard error of the mean across each outlier for every dataset (NA: one valid counterfactual only). Lower is better. k : neighbourhood size in LOF. 10 representative datasets out of 50 total, the full table is available in extended material [2].

Dataset	%NAF	k	DCFO	Baycon
			$\mu \pm \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$	$\mu \pm \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$
confidence	0.33	20	0.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1
wine	0.08	10	0.7 ± 0.2	1.1 ± 0.3
wine-quality-white	0.27	20	1.1 ± 0.2	1.6 ± 0.2
wdbc	0.13	20	2.1 ± 0.4	3.2 ± 0.7
diggle table a1	0.25	15	0.14 ± 0.01	0.2 ± 0.1
libras move	0.28	20	$0.61 \pm \text{NA}$	$1.68 \pm \text{NA}$
kc3	0.26	15	0.8 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 0.3
kc2	0.14	10	0.8 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.3
mfeat-zernike	0.26	10	1.7 ± 0.6	3.0 ± 1.0
ecoli	0.14	15	2.1 ± 0.5	2.4 ± 0.5

Table 4: Validity for limited actionable features. %NAF: percentage of non-actionable features. Note: no standard error of the mean as results are per-dataset and not per-instance.

	%NAF	k	DCFO	Baycon
confidence	0.33	20	1.00	1.00
wine	0.08	10	1.00	1.00
wine-quality-white	0.27	20	0.95	0.90
wdbc	0.13	20	1.00	0.94
diggle table a1	0.25	15	1.00	1.00
libras move	0.28	20	1.00	1.00
kc3	0.26	15	0.68	0.40
kc2	0.14	10	0.78	0.65
mfeat-zernike	0.26	10	1.00	1.00
ecoli	0.14	15	0.96	0.92

validity (how often outputs are correct), and diversity (ability to propose multiple alternatives). Finally, we used proximity and validity again to assess DCFO’s handling of non-actionable features.

Future work can investigate extending DCFO to other variants of LOF [1, 28, 41]. Furthermore, DCFO could be extended with modifications that aim to minimise the number of features changed.

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References

- [1] Omar Alghushairy, Raed Alsin, Terence Soule, and Xiaogang Ma. 2020. A review of local outlier factor algorithms for outlier detection in big data streams. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing* 5, 1 (2020), 1–22.
- [2] Tommaso Amico, Pernille Matthews, Lena Krieger, Arthur Zimek, and Ira Assent. 2025. DCFO: Density-Based Counterfactuals for Outliers - Additional Material. arXiv:2512.10659 [cs.LG] <https://arxiv.org/abs/2512.10659>
- [3] Alastair Anderberg, James Bailey, Ricardo J. G. B. Campello, Michael E. Houle, Henrique O. Marques, Milos Radovanovic, and Arthur Zimek. 2024. Dimensionality-Aware Outlier Detection. In *SDM*. SIAM, 652–660.
- [4] Fabrizio Angiulli, Fabio Fasseti, Simona Nisticó, and Luigi Palopoli. 2023. Counterfactual explanations for outliers via subspaces density contrastive loss. In *International Conference on Discovery Science*. Springer, Cham, Switzerland, 159–173.
- [5] Fabrizio Angiulli, Themis Palpanas, and Corrado Pizzuti. 2009. Detecting outlying properties of exceptional objects. In *Proceedings of the 15th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. ACM, 17–26.
- [6] Franz Aurenhammer and Rolf Klein. 1996. *Voronoi Diagrams*. Citeseer, Herndon, VA.
- [7] Vic Barnett and Toby Lewis. 1994. *Outliers in Statistical Data* (3 ed.). Wiley, New York, NY.
- [8] Aditya Bhattacharya, Tim Vanherwegen, and Katrien Verbert. 2025. “Show Me How”: Benefits and Challenges of Agent-Augmented Counterfactual Explanations for Non-Expert Users. In *Proceedings of the 33rd ACM Conference on User Modeling, Adaptation and Personalization*. ACM, Dublin, Ireland, 174–184.
- [9] Markus M Breunig, Hans-Peter Kriegel, Raymond T Ng, and Jörg Sander. 2000. LOF: Identifying Density-based Local Outliers. In *Proceedings of the 2000 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data*. ACM, Dallas, Texas, USA, 93–104.
- [10] Eugenio F Cabral, Braulio V Sánchez Vinces, Guilherme DF Silva, Jörg Sander, and Robson LF Cordeiro. 2025. Efficient outlier detection in numerical and categorical data. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 39, 3 (2025), 1–46.
- [11] Ricardo J. G. B. Campello, Davoud Moulavi, Arthur Zimek, and Jörg Sander. 2015. Hierarchical Density Estimates for Data Clustering, Visualization, and Outlier Detection. *ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data* 10, 1 (2015), 5:1–5:51. doi:10.1145/2733381
- [12] Guilherme Oliveira Campos, Arthur Zimek, Jörg Sander, Ricardo J. G. B. Campello, Barbora Micenkova, Erich Schubert, Ira Assent, and Michael E. Houle. 2016. On the Evaluation of Unsupervised Outlier Detection: Measures, Datasets, and an Empirical Study. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 30, 4 (2016), 891–927. doi:10.1007/s10618-015-0444-8
- [13] Sanjay Chawla and Aristides Gionis. 2013. k-Means-: A Unified Approach to Clustering and Outlier Detection. In *Proceedings of the 13th SIAM International Conference on Data Mining*. SIAM, Austin, Texas, USA, 189–197.
- [14] Arun Das and Paul Rad. 2020. Opportunities and Challenges in Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): A Survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.11371* (2020). arXiv:2006.11371 [urlhttps://arxiv.org/abs/2006.11371](https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.11371).
- [15] Debanjan Datta, Feng Chen, and Naren Ramakrishnan. 2022. Framing Algorithmic Recourse for Anomaly Detection. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*. ACM, Washington, DC, USA, 283–293.
- [16] Janez Demsar. 2006. Statistical Comparisons of Classifiers over Multiple Data Sets. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 7 (2006), 1–30. [urlhttps://jmlr.org/papers/v7/demsar06a.html](https://jmlr.org/papers/v7/demsar06a.html)
- [17] Alessandro Fontanella, Grant Mair, Joanna Wardlaw, Emanuele Trucco, and Amos Storkey. 2024. Diffusion Models for Counterfactual Generation and Anomaly Detection in Brain Images. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 43, 4 (2024), 1123–1135.
- [18] Frank E Grubbs. 1969. Procedures for detecting outlying observations in samples. *Technometrics* 11, 1 (1969), 1–21.
- [19] Riccardo Guidotti. 2024. Counterfactual Explanations and How to Find Them: Literature Review and Benchmarking. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 38, 5 (2024), 2770–2824.
- [20] Songqiao Han, Xiyang Hu, Hailiang Huang, Minqi Jiang, and Yue Zhao. 2022. Ad-bench: Anomaly detection benchmark. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 35 (2022), 32142–32159.
- [21] Victoria Hodge and Jim Austin. 2004. A survey of outlier detection methodologies. *Artificial Intelligence Review* 22 (2004), 85–126.
- [22] Xiayan Ji, Anton Xue, Eric Wong, Oleg Sokolsky, and Insup Lee. 2024. AR-Pro: Counterfactual Explanations for Anomaly Repair with Formal Properties. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 37 (2024), 16133–16159.
- [23] Wen Jin, Anthony K. H. Tung, Jiawei Han, and Wei Wang. 2006. Ranking Outliers Using Symmetric Neighborhood Relationship. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 3918 (Advances in Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (PAKDD 2006))*. Springer, Singapore, 577–593.
- [24] Kentaro Kanamori, Takuya Takagi, Ken Kobayashi, and Hiroki Arimura. 2020. DACE: Distribution-Aware Counterfactual Explanation by Mixed-Integer Linear Optimization. In *Proceedings of the 29th International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*. IJCAI Organization, Yokohama, Japan, 2855–2862.
- [25] E. Michael Knorr and Raymond T. Ng. 1999. Finding intensional knowledge of distance-based outliers. *ACM SIGMOD Record* 28, 2 (1999), 14–25.
- [26] Dieter Kraft. 1988. A software package for sequential quadratic programming. *Forschungsbericht- Deutsche Forschungs- und Versuchsanstalt für Luft- und Raumfahrt* (1988).
- [27] Hans-Peter Kriegel, Matthias Schubert, and Arthur Zimek. 2008. Angle-based outlier detection in high-dimensional data. In *KDD*. ACM, 444–452.
- [28] Hans-Peter Kriegel, Peer Kröger, Erich Schubert, and Arthur Zimek. 2009. LoOP: Local Outlier Probabilities. In *Proceedings of the 18th ACM Conference on Information and Knowledge Management*. ACM, Hong Kong, China, 1649–1652.
- [29] Dan Ley, Umang Bhatt, and Adrian Weller. 2022. Diverse, Global and Amortised Counterfactual Explanations for Uncertainty Estimates. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 36. AAAI Press, Virtual Conference, 7390–7398.
- [30] Zhong Li, Yuxuan Zhu, and Matthijs Van Leeuwen. 2023. A Survey on Explainable Anomaly Detection. *ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data* 18, 1 (2023), 1–54.
- [31] Angelica Liguori, Ettore Ritacco, Francesco Sergio Pisani, and Giuseppe Manco. 2024. Robust Anomaly Detection via Adversarial Counterfactual Generation. *Knowledge and Information Systems* 66, 12 (2024), 7437–7468.
- [32] Ramaravind K Mothilal, Amit Sharma, and Chenhao Tan. 2020. Explaining Machine Learning Classifiers through Diverse Counterfactual Explanations. In *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*. ACM, Barcelona, Spain, 607–617.
- [33] Michael Müller, Matthias Zehlke, and Matthias Kirchberg. 2012. OutRules: A framework for outlier descriptions in multiple context spaces. In *2012 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining*. IEEE, 867–872.
- [34] Jorge Nocedal and Stephen J Wright. 1999. *Numerical Optimization*. (1999).
- [35] Egawati Panjei, Le Gruenwald, Eleazar Leal, Christopher Nguyen, and Shejuti Silvia. 2022. A survey on outlier explanations. *The VLDB Journal* 31, 5 (2022), 977–1008.
- [36] Rafael Poyiadzi, Kacper Sokol, Raul Santos-Rodriguez, Tjil De Bie, and Peter Flach. 2020. FACE: Feasible and Actionable Counterfactual Explanations. In *Proceedings of the AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 344–350.
- [37] Sridhar Ramaswamy, Rajeev Rastogi, and Kyuseok Shim. 2000. Efficient algorithms for mining outliers from large data sets. In *Proceedings of the 2000 ACM SIGMOD international conference on Management of data*. 427–438.
- [38] Philipp Röchner, Henrique O. Marques, Ricardo J. G. B. Campello, and Arthur Zimek. 2024. Evaluating outlier probabilities: assessing sharpness, refinement, and calibration using stratified and weighted measures. *Data Min. Knowl. Discov* 38, 6 (2024), 3719–3757.
- [39] Piotr Romashov, Martin Gjoreski, Kacper Sokol, Maria Vanina Martinez, and Marc Langheinrich. 2022. BayCon: Model-agnostic Bayesian Counterfactual Generator. In *Proceedings of the 31st International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI)*. IJCAI Organization, Macau, China, 740–746.
- [40] Chris Russell. 2019. Efficient Search for Diverse Coherent Explanations. In *Proceedings of the Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*. ACM, Atlanta, GA, USA, 20–28.
- [41] Erich Schubert, Arthur Zimek, and Hans-Peter Kriegel. 2014. Local Outlier Detection Reconsidered: A Generalized View on Locality with Applications to Spatial, Video, and Network Outlier Detection. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* 28, 1 (2014), 190–237. doi:10.1007/S10618-012-0300-Z
- [42] Deborah Sulem, Michele Donini, Muhammad Bilal Zafar, Francois-Xavier Aubet, Jan Gasthaus, Tim Januschowski, Sanjiv Das, Krishnaram Kenthapadi, and Cedric Archambeau. 2022. Diverse Counterfactual Explanations for Anomaly Detection in Time Series. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.11103* (2022). arXiv:2203.11103 [urlhttps://arxiv.org/abs/2203.11103](https://arxiv.org/abs/2203.11103).
- [43] Violeta Teodora Trifunov, Maha Shadaydeh, Björn Barz, and Joachim Denzler. 2021. Anomaly Attribution of Multivariate Time Series Using Counterfactual Reasoning. In *2021 20th IEEE International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications (ICMLA)*. IEEE, Punta Cana, Dominican Republic, 166–172.
- [44] Joaquin Vanschoren, Jan N Van Rijn, Bernd Bischl, and Luis Torgo. 2014. OpenML: Networked Science in Machine Learning. *ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter* 15, 2 (2014), 49–60.
- [45] Sahil Verma, Varich Boonsanong, Minh Hoang, Keegan Hines, John Dickerson, and Chirag Shah. 2024. Counterfactual Explanations and Algorithmic Recourses for Machine Learning: A Review. *Comput. Surveys* 56, 12 (2024), 1–42.
- [46] Sahil Verma, John Dickerson, and Keegan Hines. 2020. Counterfactual explanations for machine learning: A review. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.10596* 2, 1 (2020), 1. arXiv:2010.10596 [urlhttps://arxiv.org/abs/2010.10596](https://arxiv.org/abs/2010.10596).
- [47] Braulio Valentin Sanchez Vinces, Erich Schubert, Arthur Zimek, and Robson L. F. Cordeiro. 2025. A comparative evaluation of clustering-based outlier detection.

Data Min. Knowl. Discov. 39, 2 (2025), 13.

- [48] Hongzhi Wang, Mohamed Jaward Bah, and Mohamed Hammad. 2019. Progress in outlier detection techniques: A survey. *IEEE Access* 7 (2019), 107964–108000.
- [49] Shoki Yamao, Ken Kobayashi, Kentaro Kanamori, Takuya Takagi, Yuichi Ike, and Kazuhide Nakata. 2024. Distribution-Aligned Sequential Counterfactual Explanation with Local Outlier Factor. In *Pacific Rim International Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. Springer, Nagoya, Japan, 243–256.
- [50] Peng Zhou, Qihui Tong, Shiji Chen, Yunyun Zhang, and Xindong Wu. 2025. EACE: Explain Anomaly via Counterfactual Explanations. *Pattern Recognition* 164 (2025), 111532.
- [51] Arthur Zimek and Peter Filzmoser. 2018. There and back again: Outlier detection between statistical reasoning and data mining algorithms. *WIREs Data Mining Knowl. Discov.* 8, 6 (2018). doi:10.1002/WIDM.1280

Appendices

A Multiple Counterfactual Algorithm

Section 4.1 describes how DCFO can be extended to produce multiple diverse and proximal counterfactuals by exploiting the region structure explored during optimisation. Algorithm 2 formalises this procedure. After running DCFO once to obtain the closest counterfactual and the associated exploration list, the algorithm iterates over the boundary points discovered during optimisation. Each point is used to initialise a new constrained optimisation, and a counterfactual is accepted if its region has not yet been represented in the output. The process terminates either when the requested number of counterfactuals is reached or when the exploration list is exhausted.

Algorithm 2: DCFOmultiple($p_i, d, k, \mathcal{D}, t, n$)

Input : Outlier p_i , distance function d , LOF parameter k , dataset \mathcal{D} , threshold t , number of counterfactuals c .

Output: Counterfactual List, $cfList(p_i)$

Initialise counterfactual list, $cfList \leftarrow []$;

Initialise counterfactuals' regions list, $regionsList \leftarrow []$;

Let $cf(p_i) \leftarrow DCFO(p_i, d, k, \mathcal{D}, t)$;

Let $ExpList$ the exploration list from $DCFO(p_i, d, k, \mathcal{D}, t)$;

$cfList.append(cf(p_i))$;

$regionsList.append(\mathcal{K}(cf(p_i)))$;

while $length(cfList) < n$ **and** $ExpList > 0$ **do**

$x_i \leftarrow ExpList.pop()$;

$cf(x_i) \leftarrow DCFO(x_i, d, k, \mathcal{D}, t)$;

if $\mathcal{K}(cf(x_i))$ *not in* $regionsList$ **then**

$regionsList.append(\mathcal{K}(cf(x_i)))$;

$cfList.append(cf(x_i))$;

end

end

B Counterfactuals' Empirical Evaluation

Due to space constraints, the complete experimental tables for all 50 datasets are not included in this paper. Instead, they are made available in extended material [2]. Below, we briefly summarise the full results corresponding to each experimental setting.

Run Time Critical Difference Diagram

Figure 5: Run time Critical Difference diagram comparing run times across counterfactual generation methods. Baseline, the simplest algorithm, consistently ranks first. DCFO ranks higher than EACE and Baycon, with the result being statistically significant under Nemenyi's test.

Counterfactuals' Proximity. Section 4.1 showed that DCFO achieves better proximity than competing methods. The full proximity results for all 50 datasets, available in extended material [2], confirm this trend. DCFO consistently attains the smallest perturbations across datasets, with only two exceptions, *longley* and *chscase vine 1* where BayCon performs better.

Counterfactuals' Validity. Table 1 in this paper reported validity scores for 10 datasets. The complete validity results for all 50 datasets are available in the extended material [2]. These confirm that DCFO provides a valid counterfactual for every outlier in every dataset (average validity = 1). Baseline ranks second, while BayCon and especially EACE show lower validity overall.

Non-actionable Features: Proximity. Proximity results under non-actionable feature constraints, for all 50 datasets, are available in the extended material [2]. DCFO remains the best-performing method in most cases, with exceptions limited to *longley* and *blood-transfusion*. These results mirror those in Table 2, Figure 3 and Table 5 in the extended material [2], confirming DCFO's robustness even when a subset of the features cannot be modified.

Non-actionable Features: Validity. The full validity results under non-actionable features are provided in the extended material [2]. Compared with the unconstrained settings, validity decreases for multiple datasets, reflecting the increased difficulty imposed by feature immutability. Regardless, DCFO consistently outperforms BayCon across all datasets.

C Run Time Analysis

Although LOF is a non-continuous function, DCFO successfully employs gradient-based optimisation, which is typically faster than Bayesian or genetic algorithms. We benchmark DCFO's run time against all competing methods. The complete run time tables for all 50 datasets are available in our supplementary material as well [2].

Table 5 in the repository reports the average run time per outlier for each dataset. Because datasets vary widely in dimensionality, size, and density structure, we do not compute an overall mean across datasets. Instead, we aggregate the results using a critical difference diagram, shown in Figure 5. For DCFO, EACE, and Baseline we retrieve one counterfactual per outlier, while Baycon generates multiple counterfactuals by default.

The results clearly show that Baseline is computationally the fastest method, since it only moves each outlier to its nearest inlier—a simple and inexpensive heuristic. Both Table 9 in the extended material [2] and Figure 5 demonstrate that DCFO’s gradient-based procedure is consistently more efficient than the Bayesian optimisation used by Baycon and the genetic search employed by EACE.

D LOF’s Parameters Sensitivity Analysis

We repeat the comparison from Section 4.1 while expanding the hyperparameter search over LOF’s k values and anomaly thresholds. The complete sensitivity tables for proximity and validity are available in the extended material [2] and confirm that DCFO’s performance is robust across LOF parameters. The trends observed in the paper remain consistent over the extended hyperparameter grid.

E Space Partition Ablation Study

In order to properly analyse the benefits of the space partition, we run our gradient-based constrained optimisation without giving the algorithm access to regions, we call this baseline FullOpt. As the non-continuity of the LOF function would suggest, FullOpt fails to retrieve counterfactuals when the algorithm leaves the starting region. When instead the counterfactual is close enough to the original instance to be in the same region, FullOpt works with a fully differentiable function and finds the same counterfactual as DCFO. Table 10 and Table 11 in the extended material [2] show FullOpt’s proximity and validity results. The tables highlight how FullOpt fails to reliably produce counterfactual explanations as, without access to regions, LOF’s being non-continuous prevents the gradient-based optimiser to find a valid solution. Validity is indeed very low, the few cases for which FullOpt finds a counterfactual is when the optimisation never leaves the starting region and thus spans a differentiable area. In these cases FullOpt finds the same counterfactual as DCFO while it fails to output a result in all cases where the optimisation explores more than one region.